

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.760 Max: 62.958	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1393 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 2130-2131	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 333
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DEFINITION Eastern Wall in Room No 6	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1327	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1475	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive		
Anthropic <input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	Geological <input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td>Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry): SU 1390
Is abutted by: SU 1386,	Abuts:
Is covered by: SU 1327	Covers: 1471
Is cut by: SU 1347	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1475

OBSERVATIONS Excavated by trowel + pick, dry conditions

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: South-western quarter of area B, Eastern wall of room No. 6.
Shape: Rectangular wall, aligned with wall 1185 and 1469

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: North, South

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction) (?)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) 5-10 cm Medium (range) 15-20 cm Large (range) 25-45 cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

l = 184 cm h = 23 cm w = 50 cm

Description:

Small section of wall starts in South from southernmost wall & extends indefinitely into cut for Tomb of SU 1347 → not clearly defined beyond SU 1347 (cut) (cut toward North irregularly shaped rocks w/ no binding agent present

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Appears to be the eastern wall of Room No 6 & the western wall of the room in SU 1386.
The wall in SU 1393 perpendicularly binds w/ the southern wall in SU 1390.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Brandon Tomaso on July 20, 2011

Revised by CHM on 1.18.2011

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Entered by _____ on _____